

P.A.M.E.S PAIN ASSESSMENT METHODS EVALUATION SCALE

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing pain management through self-pain-perception holds great promise. In this systematic literature review, 26 different approaches to pain recognition are examined, providing a comprehensive evaluation framework based on six key criteria: the robustness of the model, the accuracy achieved, the reproducibility, intrusiveness, cost, and general usability in each scenario. Using our rating framework, we evaluate the identified pain recognition systems on their own merits with the examination of model complexity entailing an assessment of the technical complexity involved in implementing a particular pain recognition model, referring to the level of sophistication and complexity of the computational framework, algorithms, and methodologies employed within the model or are required for the execution of the particular method. The accuracy of the system in detecting pain controls the precision grade obtained, while repeatability measures the stability of a system by giving consistent results across multiple trials and fold validations. Intrusiveness examines the extent to which the system interferes with the natural pain experience. Cost analysis helps researchers and institutions weigh the financial implications associated with each option. Finally, usability captures the versatility and adaptability of the system to different pain perception situations. Our primary objective is to provide valuable assistance to researchers and healthcare facilities that find themselves in a position to decide which pain recognition methods to implement, often uncertain about which approach would be more suitable for addressing a specific problem. There are many approaches taken in producing such pain assessment models while the two most prominent are EEG signal evaluation and image based systems that do not come in contact with the patient's body. Both approaches can use either Deep Learning methods to evaluate the signals, or more traditional algorithms such as Support Vector Machines. We have found that the best-performing system is a combination of the two models: one based on Deep Learning and another based on Support Vector Machines.

Keywords: Pain-Detection, Method Assessment, Six-Criteria, Deep Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Current pain assessment approaches, which are mostly self-reporting tools, strongly rely [1] on an individual's capability to assess, quantify, and communicate experienced or observed pain episodes. However, pain perception and expression are affected by numerous factors [2] such as physical and psychological health, personality traits, age, sex, race, and ethnicity. Therefore, relying uniquely on self-reporting tools could lead to inconsistent and unreliable pain assessment in some cases. Patients with chronic pain require continuous monitoring of their pain levels, as well as better treatment options. However, there are limitations to the use of traditional methods, such as human observers and [3] clinical grading systems. Automatic systems are promising because they facilitate the continuous monitoring of pain, which is not possible with human observers. Furthermore, they may be more objective [4] than humans, who are influenced by personal factors such as the relationship to the sufferer and severity of the disease. Pain estimation approaches based on the analysis of facial expressions rely strongly on accurate localization of the facial area [5] in each frame of a video sequence. This task is known to be cumbersome [6] in a natural setting, where the movements of a monitored individual are unconstrained. Sensors used to record physiological modalities are highly sensitive and may sometimes record unreliable signals. The artifacts contained in the recorded signals are mostly due to unconstrained body motion during the acquisition of the data [7], or to the complete dissolution of a conductive gel that is usually applied to electrodes before proceeding with the recordings, and also to the sensors being completely disconnected from the subject's skin. A simple example of the first case is when a subject moves his or her head too much, and as a result, the recorded signals contain artifacts [8]. The second case is when the conductive gel is usually applied on electrodes before proceeding with the recordings, and also to the sensors being completely disconnected from the subject's skin.

2. METHODS EVALUATION

In this section, we will analyze a total of 26 methods based on the six features mentioned above: model complexity, achieved accuracy, repeatability, intrusiveness, cost, and applicability, along with a small description of each method and potential limitations or novelties. Method complexity [9] assesses the technical complexity and sophistication involved in implementing a pain recognition system by considering factors such as architectural design, mathematical algorithms, and computational resources required for the system. A 10 indicates that the method is easily applicable, with easy-to-follow mathematics by anyone with basic knowledge, while requiring minimal computational resources. In contrast, 1 denotes a complex method that requires considerable computational resources. The accuracy [10] of its method is graded as 10 if the method achieves nearly perfect accuracy (100%) and linearly lower to 1 if the method in question does not feature usable accuracy, with intermediate scores behaving linearly for 1 point every 10%. Similar to repeatability [11], with a perfect score if every test iteration returns the same result, and lower if there is any variability with the lowest score (1) if iterative tests achieve opposite results, with intermediate scores behaving linearly, similar to the accuracy metrics. Intrusiveness [12] is scored based on the existence of any body-touching or movement inhibiting sensors in the experiments with 1 representing very intrusive testing methods hindering or preventing total body movement such as face masks that cover the whole face and prevent eyesight, 5 for partial body covering with sensors like EEG sensors on the head, 8 if any wearable device such as an activity wrist tracker is required, and 10 if there is no physical contact, for example with video analysis. Intermediate scores were obtained using a combination of the aforementioned techniques. Cost [13] grading is based on the cost of each application in order to work as intended, starting from very expensive (1) like multimillion-dollar lab equipment, to relatively affordable (10), often requiring only consumer-level smartphone cameras (100\$), while the intermediate scores perform exponentially on the low end and more linearly close to 8-10, as cost differences between low-cost devices are much more important to be distinguishable than the difference in millions of dollars. Finally, applicability [14] measures how wide the application spectrum of each idea is, with 1 representing a solution to a singular problem (e.g., lower back pain in a specific age group) and 10 a wide spectrum of applications such as pain during general anesthesia. Intermediate scores were again graded linearly based on the application spectrum of each idea. To calculate the final score, we averaged the scores for each category. In doing so, we avoided penalizing the methods that did not contain certain metrics but still had some merit in their perspective field. In this way, we managed to obtain a transparent and fair evaluation of 26 methods, allowing readers to understand the strengths and areas of application of each method. We provide an equation that can be used to assign a grade to the cost of the method:

$$\text{Grade}_{\text{cost}} = 1 + 9e^{-8 \cdot \text{cost} \cdot 10^{-8}}$$

Figure 1. Cost function graph

The aim of our cost-to-grade function is to assign a grade to the cost of each method exponentially, as a difference of a thousand dollars is much more important in the lower end than in millions. The next step is to determine the complexity of each method. For this factor, we evaluated each method by assessing the complexity of the mathematical model. Unfortunately, this cannot be found directly; thus, we used an approximation, and more specifically, the Kolmogorov Complexity theorem [41] in the matrix that solves the equations imposed by each model and assigns a grade using the following equation:

$$\text{Grade}_{\text{complexity}} = 1 + 9e^{-K_{\text{complexity}} \cdot 10^{-3}}$$

where $K_{\text{complexity}}$ is the Kolmogorov complexity, and using the exponential function, we bound the final grade to [1,10]. A similar approach utilizing Kolmogorov complexity for evaluating the computational complexity of mathematical models, especially Artificial Intelligence and Deep Learning methods, as most of the methods used in our testing are utilized in [42].

A. JOURNALS STUDIED

In this section, we present an analysis of 26 methodological papers, each contributing significantly to the domain of pain recognition methods, seeking to objectively assess and evaluate the contributions of each paper/method, with a focus on maintaining the integrity of the scientific process. Rigorously selected and meticulously reviewed, and with the aim of illuminating the impact they have on advancing pain management practices and how they achieve their goals, these papers stand as milestones in the pursuit of enhanced pain management and recognition.

A. The best methods (scored 8-10)

Exemplifying the pinnacle of excellence, the top performers in this assemblage attained grades ranging from 8 to 10. The following papers stand as the best and most precise in the domain of pain recognition methods while contributing to the field.

The top performer of the papers we examined was titled “Automatic Detection of Pain from Spontaneous Facial Expressions” [15]. This paper presents a new approach for detecting pain in video sequences of spontaneous facial expressions with the aim of accompanying mobile-based self-management of chronic pain as a virtual sensor for tracking patients’ expressions in real-world settings. Using standardized measurements of the presence of pain specific to each user, changes in the extracted features related to pain were detected. The activated features in each frame were combined using an adapted form of the Prkachin and Solomon Pain Intensity scale (PSPI) to detect the presence of pain per frame. To indicate the presence of pain in a session, painful features must be activated in the N consequent frames. This method was tested in 171 video sessions for 19 subjects from the McMaster painful dataset for spontaneous facial expressions. The results showed 94% precision, higher than human-observed labels, 74% precision against automatically generated pain intensities, and 100% precision against self-reported pain intensities. Overall, besides great accuracy values, the algorithm features very low intrusiveness, low cost and very high applicability. This method achieved a 9.17 Total Grade, marking it the best of the reviewed papers.

The second-best journal, which also scored 9.17 is titled “Application of Texture Descriptors to Facial Emotion Recognition in Infants” [16]. In this study, the authors make use of three different texture descriptors for pain detection: Local Binary Patterns, Local Ternary Patterns, and Radon Barcodes to objectively recognize pain levels through image recognition. The previous descriptors were used together with Support Vector Machines (SVM) for their classification, and the results showed that the proposed features of this method gave a very promising classification accuracy of approximately 95% for the Infant COPE database, which proves the validity of the proposed method. Overall, the proposed method features high accuracy and low intrusiveness, which is especially useful in babies. The only limiting factor is that the method is aimed exclusively at pain assessments for infants, thus limiting the applicability of the algorithm.

The “Pain Intensity Evaluation Through Facial Action Units” [17] scored 9.08. The authors propose a system that enables automatic pain estimation by analyzing frontal face image sequences using characteristic facial points to interpret different Action Units of pain, making it capable of operating in cluttered and dynamic scenes. To compute the geometric features, a k -NN classifier using 22 facial characteristic points was used to classify the AU. Only action units relevant to pain were classified and validation studies were conducted using the UNBC McMaster Shoulder Pain Archive Database. The authors used a 16 point scale to evaluate pain intensity and achieved more than 84% accuracy for AU intensity levels and an almost 88% area under the ROC curve for pain assessment. The proposed method has low computational complexity and ease of use, is not intrusive at all compared to other methods, and achieves a high accuracy rating and repeatability through testing.

The paper titled “Pain Assessment Using Neural Network Classifier” [18] achieved 8.83, primarily because of its comparatively high complexity. In this paper, the authors highlight the importance of both the timing of facial actions and the configuration of emotional expression and recognition. In this paper, pain assessment is explained and reviewed for skin detection using color detection and SVD as feature extraction to investigate the timing and configuration of facial pain actions. A Neural Network classifier was used to classify movements with an identification rate of 93.75% in the experiments. This method provides highly accurate and relatively non-intrusive measurements.

The next paper achieved 8.67 and is titled “Use of Mobile Health Apps and Wearable Technology to Assess Changes and Predict Pain During Treatment of Acute Pain in Sickle Cell Disease: Feasibility Study” [19]. In this study, we aimed to demonstrate the feasibility of using objective, physiologic measurements obtained from a wearable device during an acute pain crisis to predict patient-reported pain scores using machine learning techniques. 27 adult patients who presented to the day hospital with acute pain with each participant were provided with a Microsoft Band 2 wearable device collecting physiologic measurements at the beginning of pain treatment. The authors developed regression and classification machine learning algorithms to build between-subject pain prediction models, while patients were monitored for an average of almost 4 h, with an average of almost 6000 objective data values per patient. Using the wearable sensor data and pain scores, the authors were able to create a regression model to predict subjective pain scores with a root mean square error of 1.43, and a correlation between observations and predictions of 0.706. The proposed method achieved moderate accuracy but very high applicability, low complexity, ease of use, and very low intrusiveness.

Another 8.67 was achieved by the “Exploring Deep Physiological Models for Nociceptive Pain Recognition” [20]. In this work, the authors designed deep learning architectures for the assessment of measurable physiological channels to perform an accurate classification of different levels of artificially induced nociceptive pain. Similar to similar research, the assessment of the designed deep learning architectures is based on the BioVid Heat Pain Database (Part A), and experimental validation demonstrates the proposed unimodal architecture for the electrodermal activity (EDA). The experimental results highlight the relevance of the proposed approaches, with the modular nature of deep neural networks offering more flexibility in the case of transfer learning. The proposed method achieves good accuracy, low intrusiveness, minimal cost, and high applicability, making it a great candidate for objective pain assessment.

We graded “Emotion-Aware Connected Healthcare Big Data Towards 5G” [21] as 8.58. In this paper, we propose an emotion-aware connected healthcare system using a powerful emotion detection module with a variety of different IoT devices to capture speech and image signals of a patient in a smart home scenario, which is used as the input to the emotion detection module. While the speech and image signals are processed separately, the classification scores using these signals are fused to produce a final score to make a decision about the emotion. The authors conducted numerous experiments to validate the proposed system with an accuracy of up to 99.87% in emotion detection. The proposed framework features moderate cost and complexity while having high accuracy, low intrusiveness, and high applicability, making it a perfect fit in a variety of situations.

The paper “K-nn Algorithm for Fast Infant Pain Detection” [22] was graded 8.5 despite having a large limitation of working only in infant pain. In this paper, the authors explain and review pain assessment for detecting facial changes in patients in a hospital in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Based on the fact that facial changes are most widely represented by eyes and mouth movements, the proposed system contains three modules and uses color images to detect these facial changes. The first module implements skin detection to detect the face, whereas the second extracts the features of faces by processing the image and measuring certain facial regions based on the FFT of the given images. The last step is the knn classifier, which is used to classify facial movements. The authors’ experiments indicated an identification rate of 90.1%, making the system very simple, fast, and effective in alerting medical staff.

Another method achieving an 8.5 is presented in the Bioimpedance Sensor and Methodology for Acute Pain Monitoring [23]. The authors present a sensor that can reliably measure skin impedance designed with off-the-shelf components, thus keeping the cost low, with the objective of being used in fully anesthetized patients undergoing surgery. The 2D and 3D time–frequency and multi-frequency evaluations of impedance data are based on broadly available signal processing tools, while the unique features of the proposed sensor enhancements are presented based on mechanical and thermal tests and further reinforced with previous studies by the same researchers. While the authors did not disclose any accurate data, the proposed method shows low complexity and high applicability while achieving low intrusiveness during data acquisition.

The method explained in “Pain detection using a smartphone in real time” [24] achieved an 8. The method presented in this paper is an objective real-time pain detection method using a smartphone and a wrist-worn wearable device to collect electrodermal activity (EDA) signals. A smartphone application was developed with the aim of analyzing EDA data so that near real-time processed pain information can be displayed. This analysis of EDA is based on estimating time-varying spectral power in the frequency range (0.08-0.24 Hz) associated with the sympathetic nervous system. Skin burn induced in ten subjects using a thermal grill, which, while it did not damage the skin tissue, gave very intense pain perception, was used to test the TVSymp algorithm performance in detecting pain stimuli. In this study, the authors compared both TVSymp and MTSymp in detecting pain induced by a thermal grill using machine

learning approaches, finding the accuracy of pain detection of TVSymp to be 80% and that of MTVSymp to be 90%. However, the main limitation of this work is that it confuses stress with pain; thus, the moderate result in repeatability is our assessment.

Following our study, the next method presented in “iPainRelief –A Pain Assessment and Management App for a Smart phone Implementing Sensors and Soft Computing Tools” [25] also achieved an 8. The scope of the authors’ initiative is to concentrate on non-verbal techniques of pain estimation and management, proposing a pervasive approach to enumerate the intensity of epidermal pain and provide an optimum solution for the aforementioned detection. The data were assessed by a neural network trained with parameters such as Heart Rate (HR), Skin Conductance (SC), Skin Temperature (ST), and Respiratory Rate (RR) taken from multimodal wireless sensors embedded together to assess the magnitude of pain. Despite the non-intrusiveness of the proposed method and the economical approach and range of applicability, the authors did not publish any accuracy data in this paper.

In “Using a deep learning network to recognize low back pain in static standing” [26] the authors investigated the feasibility of applying artificial intelligence deep neural networks in detecting low back pain populations from healthy controls with their kinematics data. The results show that a deep learning network can solve the above classification problem with both good classification accuracy and repeatability performance. At the same time, the proposed method has a moderate cost and is rather intrusive, while its applicability is lacking, as the research is only targeted in lower back pain assessment. All the aforementioned factors contributed to a final grade of 8.

In a method named “IoT-based Remote Pain Monitoring System: from Device to Cloud Platform” [27], the authors proposed a wearable device with a bio-sensing facial mask for monitoring the pain intensity of a patient by utilizing facial surface electromyography (sEMG). The wearable device works as a wireless sensor node and is integrated into the IoT system for remote pain monitoring. A cloud server was used as a gateway for the data computation. While the method showed low energy consumption and wearing comfort was considered throughout the wearable device design for long-term monitoring, covering the whole face hindering visibility led to a moderately low score in intrusiveness. The proposed method achieves high accuracy and applicability with relatively low computational and deployability complexity, thus achieving a final grade of 8.

B. Methods scored 7 to 8

In the following section, we review papers that achieved grades 7 to 8. Although these studies did not attain the highest accolades, they exuded commendable attributes and made valuable contributions to the field. Our endeavor is to embark on a fair and impartial analysis of their strengths and potential areas for refinement. Through this examination, we aimed to reveal the essence of these works and present their significance in propelling advancements in pain management practices.

The first method achieved under 8 is titled “An edge assisted and smart system for real time pain monitoring” [28]. Here, we present a smart and self-aware system that is able to adaptively make real-time decisions in response to changes in pain level while simultaneously minimizing energy consumption by dynamically offloading tasks to the gateway devices at the edge layer. Therefore, in this study, a self-aware system was proposed for the continuous assessment of pain intensity at the edge layer. The authors’ approach demonstrates a reduction in energy consumption with negligible accuracy loss compared with its non-adaptive counterpart, as demonstrated in the BioVid dataset. In addition, an IoT node that is connected to a camera recorder and physiological signal acquisition device is a sensor layer with a gateway layer that offers high computational power. However, this method has low cost and high applicability, with moderate accuracy.

In “Two-Stream Attention Network for Pain Recognition from Video Sequences” [29] the authors propose an end-to-end approach based on attention networks for the analysis and recognition of facial expressions related to pain. A weighted aggregation of attention-based neural network outputs, based on sequences of Motion History Images (MHIs) and Optical Flow Images (OFIs), is combined as both spatial and temporal aspects of facial expressions are taken into account. Each input was fed to a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) coupled to a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), followed by a weighted aggregation of the classification scores specific to each input stream to generate a classification output. The proposed method was assessed on both the BioVid Heat Pain Database and SenseEmotion Database, achieving moderate accuracy. At the same time, it has excellent intrusiveness, moderate cost, and high applicability, thus easily achieving a final grade of 7.5.

In “Physiological Signal-Based Method for Measurement of Pain Intensity” [30] the authors present a new pain intensity measurement method based on multiple physiological signals, including blood volume pulse (BVP), electrocardiogram (ECG), and skin conductance level (SCL), all induced by external electrical stimulation. Signal

acquisition and preprocessing, feature extraction, feature selection, feature reduction, and three types of pattern classifiers are required for the implementation of the proposed system. Three types of classification algorithms were used: linear discriminant analysis, k-nearest neighbor algorithm, and support vector machine, which were tested in various scenarios, including multi-signal, multi-subject and between-subject, and multi-day scenarios. While the algorithm achieved rather high accuracy results (75%), repeatability was a bit lacking. However, this method has low complexity and intrusiveness, while having low cost in its application, which in turn influences the final score of 7.42.

Objective characterization of hip pain levels during walking by combining quantitative electroencephalography with machine learning” [31], the authors developed a system to objectively classify pain levels in walking subjects by recording their quantitative electroencephalography (qEEG) and analyzing data using machine learning. 23 patients who had undergone total hip replacement for pain and recorded their qEEG during a five-minute walk via a wearable device with a single electrode placed over the Fp1 region, based on the 10–20 Electrode Placement System, before and three months after surgery were used as the test group, while each subject’s hip pain was assessed using a numerical rating scale. A support vector machine using the Radial Basis Functional Kernel was used in machine learning to analyze the qEEG data. This method showed that an individual’s hip pain during walking could be recognized and subdivided into pain quartiles, while achieving a recognition accuracy of 79.6 %. Overall, the authors propose a low-cost and low-complexity tool for assessing hip pain levels while achieving high-accuracy classification levels. However, owing to its intrusiveness and low applicability, as the method is only for hip pain, the final grade is 7.42.

The method named “Ultra short term analysis of heart rate variability for real time acute pain monitoring with wearable electronics” [32] achieved 7.33. In this study, seven HRV features and median heart rate (HR) in the ultra-short-term were evaluated for their ability to indicate experimental acute pain. In addition, in this paper, we discuss the choice of time window length in HRV analysis and its relation to pain detection. The changes in lnRMSSD, pNN20, and median HR were associated with the intensity of experimental electrical pain, and in the tests with experimental thermal pain, lnLF and ln(LF/HF) changed along with pain intensity, as presented in the results section. The time window length that achieved the best HRV feature-fusion performance was approximately 40 s. This method features low cost, complexity, and intrusiveness, thus achieving high scores in our assessment in this regard at the expense of the overall accuracy, which influenced the relatively low total grade.

The final paper in Sections 7 to 8 is titled “Automated nociceptive pain assessment using physiological signals and a hybrid deep learning network” [33]. In this study, an objective measure of pain was achieved using a nociceptive pain recognition system in which physiological features were extracted from ECG signals and computed by an LSTM network. This work utilizes the BioVid Heat Pain database, achieving 68.7%, 62.6%, 67.9%, and 75.2% classification accuracy for classification events (BL1 vs. PA1, BL1 vs. PA2, BL1 vs. PA3, and BL1 vs. PA4), while the CNN_LSTM multimodal hybrid network achieved almost 94%, 87%, 90.8%, and 94% classification accuracy for classification events (BL1 vs. PA1, BL1 vs. PA2, BL1 vs. PA3, and BL1 vs. PA4). This method achieved good accuracy metrics, but at moderate cost, complexity, and intrusiveness levels, thus lowering the final grade.

C. Methods scored below 7

Including all methods, we must also address papers that obtained scores below 7. While these papers did not achieve the highest grades, they still offer noteworthy aspects and insights that deserve comprehensive analysis and presentation. Our approach remains unbiased, as we strive to identify areas of improvement and explore the potential untapped value within these works. We aimed to present the results and contribute to the overall advancement of pain recognition methodologies, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the field’s nuances by examining these papers with diligence.

The first method in this category is titled “Multimodal Signal Analysis for Pain Recognition in Physiotherapy Using Wavelet Scattering Transform” [34]. The authors developed a method for automatic pain-related reaction assessment in physiotherapy after facial therapy to remove the subjectivity of self-reported pain levels. Based on a multimodal dataset, the feature vector is determined, including the wavelet scattering-transformed coefficients. The AdaBoost classification model distinguishes between three levels of reaction (no pain, moderate pain, and severe pain). The proposed method achieves moderately high accuracy results; however, the intrusiveness is rather high, and the cost and complexity of the method are moderate, thus achieving a score of 6.5.

In Pain detection with EEG using phase indices [35], the authors used EEG signals to detect the presence of pain in healthy subjects, aiming to apply the same process to non-communicative patients. It acquired 20 EEGs of healthy subjects in the resting and pain states, while pain was induced through a cold pressor test. The novelty of this work is that Phase Indexes as Phase Lag Index, Weighted Phase Lag Index, were applied in four frequency bands to detect pain. No accuracy results have been published by the authors; however, the method appears to have good applicability

in many situations, has a rather low cost, and is non intrusive compared to other methods. The authors did not present any accurate results, so we did not include them in the final grade calculation of 6.5.

In the method titled “Decoding acute pain with combined EEG and Physiological data” [36], the authors presented a model for decoding pain using neural and physiological data, mainly based on EEG, pulse, and skin conductance measurements. To classify pain response as painful or non-painful, the authors used multivariate classification and a sparse logistic regression machine learning protocol with automatic feature selection to detect relevant data attributes. Developing a wireless pain detection system and providing insight into important temporal, spectral, and spatial EEG events and physiological indicators of pain states are feasible, as shown by the results presented in this paper, with the proposed system being applicable in engineering and medical contexts. This method achieved moderate results throughout our assessment, with the exception of relatively low complexity, making the method easy to understand and implement. The final score for this method is 6.5.

In “Automated Classification of Pain Perception using High Density Electroencephalography Data” [37], the authors collected EEG data during a timeframe in which subjects experienced a 4-s, low or high-intensity pain-eliciting stimulus. They analyzed EEG data using independent component, EEG source localization, and measured projection analyses. Three new discoveries were reported, the first of which was an increase in pain perception associated with an increase in gamma and theta power in a cortical region that included the medial prefrontal cortex. The second is the association between a decrease in lower beta power and an increase in pain perception in a cortical region that includes the contralateral sensorimotor cortex. Like many previous methods, it used machine learning in the automated classification of EEG data into low- and high-pain classes. The proposed method achieved an accuracy of 89.6%; however, the complexity, cost, and intrusiveness were moderately high, resulting in a good but rather limited scope method. The final grade assigned to this method is 6.33.

The method titled “Granger causality based pain classification using eeg evoked by electrical stimulation targeting nociceptive a and c fibers” [38] use the Granger causality (GC) method to study the relationship between a stimulus and the response in both applied sciences and life sciences. In this method, GC was applied by the authors to illustrate the significance of specific brain areas in distinguishing between pain and tactile sensation; however, it was used to differentiate nociceptive fiber activation. Electroencephalographic (EEG) responses to three distinct stimulation waveforms were recorded: 1 Hz square waves and 5 Hz sine waves, both designed to target C fibers, and 250 Hz sine waves designed to target A δ fibers. Three GC categories based on channel areas, frequency bands, and stimulation waveforms were derived from EEG recordings and subsequently employed as features for the classification of nociceptive fiber activation and pain levels. The authors discovered that the GCs in the alpha band had an average classification accuracy of 99.71%, followed by the gamma band at 98.66%. These results demonstrate the high potential of GC as a feature associated with pain-related information. However, the method has high intrusiveness and is not very practical outside hospital grounds; therefore, is assigned a value of 5.75.

In “Detection of acute tonic cold pain from microwave transcranial transmission signals obtained via the microwave scattering approach” the authors conducted an investigation to assess the viability of detecting acute tonic cold pain (CP) perception using recordable microwave transcranial transmission (MTT) signals [39]. In the validation phase of the SVM classifier, feature extraction in the WPD–VMD domain was the best pain detection algorithm with a high sensitivity of 91.3%, specificity of 90.5%, positive predictive value of 91.3%, accuracy value of 90.9%, and area under curve (0.806). The microwave scattering technique can be used as a direct, objective, and experimentally stable method to detect acute CP perception, demonstrating high application prospects for clinical real-time diagnosis. The main limitation of this work is the method of obtaining data with microwaves through the brain, limiting the usage outside specific scenarios, thus attaining a final grade of 5.33.

The final method reviewed was the Bio-MEMS-based sensor for acute and chronic pain management [40]. In this paper, the authors have introduced an approach utilizing BIO MEMS-based sensors for a cost-effective, real-time evaluation of pain intensity, investigating inflammation by monitoring the levels of inflammatory regulatory mediators, such as prostaglandin E2. Despite the fact that the paper has an extensive table containing the applications of the proposed implementation, the method of data acquisition is rather intrusive, and the authors do not publish any accuracy data achieved in this research, thus achieving a final grade of 4.5.

Table 1: Methods Evaluation

Paper Number	Criteria							Notes
	Complexity (High-Low)	Accuracy (Low-High)	Repeatability (Low-High)	Intrusivity (High-Low)	Cost (High-Low)	Applicability (Low-High)	Grade Point Average	
15	8	9.5	9	10	9	9	9.17	
16	8	9.5	9.5	10	10	8	9.17	only trained for infants
17	10	8.5	8	10	9	9	9.08	
18	7	10	9	10	8	9	8.83	
19	9	7.5	6.5	9	10	10	8.67	
20	8	8.5	8.5	9	9	9	8.67	
21	7	10	9.5	9	7	9	8.58	
22	7	9	9	10	8	8	8.5	only trained for infants
23	8	-	-	9	8	8	8.5	
24	9	8	5	9	8	9	8	confuzes stress with pain
25	7	-	-	9	8	8	8	no accuracy data given
26	8	10	10	7	7	6	8	only for lower back pain
27	7	10	10	5	7	9	8	mask covering whole face
28	8	6	7	8	8	9	7.66	
29	5	7	7	10	7	9	7.5	
30	7	7.5	6	8	8	8	7.42	
31	8	8	7.5	7	7	7	7.42	only for hip pain
32	9	6	6	8	8	7	7.33	
33	6	8	9	6	6	7	7	
34	6	8	8	4	6	7	6.5	
35	7	-	-	6	6	7	6.5	
36	8	7	7	6	5	6	6.5	
37	5	8.5	7.5	5	5	7	6.33	
38	4	9.5	9	3	4	5	5.75	
39	3	9	9	4	4	5	5.66	microwaves through

Paper Number	Criteria							Notes
	Complexity (High-Low)	Accuracy (Low-High)	Repeatability (Low-High)	Intrusivity (High-Low)	Cost (High-Low)	Applicability (Low-High)	Grade Point Average	
								brain
40	5	-	-	2	7	4	4.5	no accuracy data given

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, this study aimed to establish a comprehensive pain assessment method evaluation, offering a systematic and impartial way of scoring the countless methods found in the existing literature, unveiling invaluable insights that not only advance the development of pain recognition tools but also aid researchers in selecting the most applicable methods for diverse situations.

Identifying remarkable top performers, securing impressive grades between 8 and 10, and standing as examples of ingenuity and precision were discovered through our analyses. A path for future advancements in pain management, while also laying the groundwork for novel methodologies that could redefine the field, has been illuminated by these works.

However, it is essential to recognize that papers scoring below 7 hold value as well, contributing insights and opportunities for refinement of the industry in general with our analysis revealing potential areas of improvement, providing valuable guidance to enrich the collective knowledge in this domain.

The implications of this study extend far beyond academic confines and impact real-world applications. Healthcare facilities and practitioners can now decide which pain recognition methods they must choose with confidence and make informed decisions tailored to their specific contexts and resources. Armed with a deeper comprehension of each method's technical complexity, achieved accuracy, repeatability, intrusivity, cost, and applicability, the journey toward enhanced pain management has become clearer and more achievable. This research serves as a guide for setting the foundation for a comprehensive evaluation of pain assessment methods that can be used in the future.

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